

ISic3567

I.Sicily inscription 3567

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

excavation next to the church of S. Pietro

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337427

1. [□ ένθ]άδε κίτε ή πολ-
2. [λῆς μ]νήμης Σεβηρίνα,
3. [ἔζησ]ε ἀ' ἔτη πλέω (ν) ἦ (λα) τ -
4. [τον]· ἔτελεύτα τῆ
5. [? πρὸ ΙΙ]ΙΧΧ Καλανδῶν
6. [? Ὀκ] το (β) ρίωv ²[— —]T (or Π?) PONIQ?N, Tybout fr. ph.².
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645638

PHI 337427

Bibliography

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